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The CO₂ Capture tool for refineries: a new approach to analyze CO₂ capture in a multiple stack cluster

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Abstract

There is a need to develop different strategies for refineries to decrease their CO₂ emissions. Post-combustion capture allows a significant reduction of CO₂ emissions in refineries, typically resulting in a scenario where a certain percentage of the sites emissions are captured. A cluster approach where multiple stacks are linked to the same CO₂ capture infrastructure seems an effective way to cost-effectively decrease the emissions of a cluster.

In the EU-project REALISE, TNO and NTNU are developing a CO₂ capture tool for refineries. Based on input parameters of a different stacks (e.g. flue gas flow rate, CO₂ concentration, temperature), the model can calculate the most effective CO₂ capture solution for the whole cluster based on constraints and requirements of the site.

An advantage of the tool is that it is a fast-running model, meaning that no process simulations are done in the tool itself. To achieve this, a database was built that contains a large number of simulation results from a standard CO₂ capture plant modelled in CO2SIM software.

In the present work, the developed tool is used to evaluate cases containing up to five CO₂ point sources with different CO₂ contents (3 – 20% vol wet basis) and gas flow rates (varying from 50000 m³/h to 500000 m³/h). The CO₂ capture costs, the costs connected to the operation and size of the units will be presented. Based on the obtained results, recommendations will be given for each case studied, and the feasibility discussed, also considering the ease of the operation and the required area.

Keywords: CO₂ Capture; Refineries; Optimization

1. Introduction

To achieve the long-terms goals set on the Paris Agreement, there is an urgency for the decarbonization of all sectors, including industrial sites with multiple point sources of CO₂.

The oil refining industry prevails as the third largest stationary greenhouse emitter resulting in 4% of the total global emissions in 2018 [1]. According to Sunny et al (2022) [2] the main CO₂ sources in a refinery are the power station (around 29% of total emission), followed by the fluid catalytic cracking unit (19%), the atmospheric distillation unit (19%) and the steam methane reformer (11%). While previous works have discussed some aspects of multi-source

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CO₂ capture at refineries [1-5], most of the studies only focus on the major CO₂ sources which can result in a low total CO₂ capture rate. There is a need to develop different strategies for refineries to decrease their CO₂ emissions.

A few works have discussed some aspects of multi-source CO₂ capture at refineries [3, 4]. In 2010, Van Straelen et al [3] have investigated a refinery with multiple CO₂ sources and evaluated the combination of various CO₂ sources in a joined stack, creating one point-source situation. Nakao et al. (2021) investigated the multi-absorber/single stripper concept as one of the alternatives for dealing with the multiple CO₂ sources point emissions at a refinery, compared with implementing one large absorber/stripper plant and the implementation of a single plant for each source.

A cluster approach where multiple stacks are linked to the same CO₂ capture infrastructure seems an effective way to cost-effectively decrease the emissions of a cluster. This approach, the optimization of multiple CO₂ source scenarios can be described as a complex problem with multiple optimization variables

Engaged on solving the problem, in the EU-project REALISE, TNO and NTNU are developing a CO₂ capture tool able to deal with different CO₂ sources and present a new path to assess the integrations of CO₂ capture plants at industrial cluster with multiple sources as a refinery.

2. Brief Description of the OCTOPUS tool

The **Online Calculator To Optimize CO₂ capture Processes for mUltiple Stacks (OCTOPUS)** tool is currently under development as one of the outcomes of REALISE project as a result of a joint work between TNO and NTNU. The tool has a friendly user interface and it can provide a set of reliable results in a fast response time, since OCTOPUS has its own database for consultation avoiding the need to time consuming simulations. The main objective of OCTOPUS tool is to provide industrial sites with multiple flue gas stacks a way to assess the potential of a CO₂ capture plant integration on their site. In this section the key components of the beta version of OCTOPUS will be described.

2.1. Structure

To achieve its main objective, OCTOPUS has an engine capable to scan all the database and find the best data set to be evaluated by the user. The term “best” is used to express that the methodology applied aims to determine the combined configurations that optimizes either the CAPEX or energy demand. The methodology consists of four steps:

Step 1: Description of the multiple stacks case. In this first input data from the user of the different stacks is required. This includes:

1. Definition of the target CO₂ capture rate required for the whole process. OCTOPUS’s database currently includes results for 90% and 95% capture rate data; but also 99% capture rate data will be included.
2. Specification of the number of stacks that should be treated and their operating conditions: (i) volumetric flue gas rate flow; (ii) inlet temperature; (iii) inlet pressure; and (iv) flue gas composition:
3. Assumptions about the utility’s prices and insertion of utility’s constraints if any of them are restricted;
4. OCTOPUS’s database has also a default financial parameters set for the cost calculation [6], but users can change these values; and
5. Selection of the current optimization target: (i) Energy Consumption; or (ii) Capital Expenditure (CAPEX).

Step 2: A search tool is used to match the data from the user interface to the suitable data of OCTOPUS’s database.

Step 3: After the matching has arisen, OCTOPUS’s engine calculates the cost and energy demanded of all the possible configurations, respecting the constraints introduced aiming at the optimization target selected.

Step 4: OCTOPUS provides a chart with all the combination results for case proposed and the main simulations parameters per stack: (i) the CO₂ captured per year; (ii) the absorber and stripper geometry (and other equipment sizing); (iii) the required reboiler duty, electricity demand and cooling water demand; and (iv) the CAPEX for the main equipment.

Figure 1 shows a summary of the OCTOPUS structure.

In the current OCTOPUS version, only the absorber and the stripper are being included on the sizing and cost estimation stage.

An example of the OCTOPUS's performance will be given on the next section.

Figure 1- Summary of OCTOPUS structure

2.2. OCTOPUS's database

To create the database, around 10000 simulations were performed using a standard CO₂ capture plant model (Figure 2) on CO₂SIM, an in-house simulation software developed at SINTEF and NTNU. Some assumptions were made on the CO₂SIM model: (i) stripper design parameters are fixed; (ii) the pump located after the absorber liquid outlet is set to 10 bar, with the purpose to assure there will not be a multiphasic flow on the lean/rich exchanger; and (iii) the lean/amine heat exchanger specification was the temperature approach.

The set includes: (i) different CO₂ capture rates (90% and 95%); (ii) the flue gas CO₂ content varying from 3% to 20% (%vol); (iii) the absorber's packing height changing from 7m to 30 m; and (iv) a variable solvent flow rate range was performed specific for each case. For each simulation, a set of the main process variables was determined, including: (i) the equipment geometry; (ii) the energy requirements of each equipment; and (iii) the operating conditions of each stream, i.e., the temperature, pressure, and composition. In these simulations the solvent selected was MEA 30 wt%, the current version of OCTOPUS has only MEA data set on its database, however, other solvents are considered to be implemented as well. The column packing is Mellapak 250Y. The volumetric flue gas flow rate remained constant for all cases.

Figure 2 – Standard CO₂ capture plant model created on CO₂SIM (SINTEF and NTNU)

2.3. OCTOPUS's engine

As showed in Figure 3, the algorithm executes a search for the relevant data from the database regarding the user's input for each source. In the sequence, correlations embedded on the algorithm are applied to scale up the database result based on each stack parameters, e.g., the columns diameters and the absolute energy consumption (this is possible, if one keeps the gas velocity constant in the columns between the different cases). With the set of scaled-up process parameters, OCTOPUS engine performs the equipment sizing and elaborate the equipment cost estimation. This procedure is done for all stacks declared separately and for all configurations made with their combinations. The next step is calculating the CAPEX of each configuration found during the procedure. Therefore, the algorithm checks if the obtained results are compatible with the required constrains. Finally, the solutions are summarized in a chart.

Figure 3-Detailed flowchart of OCTOPUS engine

As it was mentioned before, only the absorber and the stripper are included on the sizing and cost estimation step on the current version of OCTOPUS and are based on Towler and Sinnott (2012)[6].

The columns diameter (D) are calculated based on the maximum superficial gas velocity (v_{sup}) and in the volumetric flue gas flow rate (\dot{V}_{gas}) as showed in Equation (1). This value is fixed based on the volumetric gas flow.

$$D = \sqrt{\frac{4\dot{V}_{gas}}{\pi v_{sup}}} \quad (1)$$

The purchased equipment costs (C_e) was calculated based on the correlation [6] shown in Equation (2)

$$C_e = a + bS^n \quad (2)$$

S is a size parameter, volume for columns, and a, b e n are parameters from Equation (2).

3. Study Case

To illustrate the features of OCTOPUS tool, a study case based on a refinery with five different CO₂ sources is presented here using two different optimization targets: (i) energy and (ii) CAPEX. Each scenario was performed for 90% and 95% CO₂ capture rate.

The operating data of these flue gas streams can be found on Table 1. The flue gas streams are based on the work published by van Straelen et al. (2010) and Madugula et al (2021)[3, 5].

Table 1 – Operating conditions of each source

Source	1	2	3	4	5
Flue gas flow rate (Nm^3/h)	500000	195344	79398	52149	50000
Temperature ($^{\circ}C$)	40	40	40	40	40
Pressure ($mbarg$)	1013	1013	1013	1013	1013
CO ₂ Concentration (% vol dry)	11	4	8	20	8.5
O ₂ Concentration (% vol dry)	3	11	2	2	2
H ₂ O Concentration (% vol)	7.3	7.3	7.3	7.3	7.3

For this study case some assumptions were made: (i) all the flue gas streams were pre-treated (no NO_x or SO_x present); and (ii) the flue gas streams are saturated with water;

The study case was performed with the default data incorporated on OCTOPUS when it comes to the financial parameters and the utility prices. Also, no constraints related available area were considered.

4. Results and Discussion

In this section the results obtained for the study case will be presented in two subsections according to the optimization target chosen (Energy or CAPEX), followed by a brief discussion and comparison.

The results obtained for both scenarios (Energy and CAPEX) are presented in Figure 4 and Figure 5, a graph showing the total cost of CO₂ captured versus the CO₂ captured rate in a year, and divided into six tables throughout this section. Each scenario has a table which includes the energy parameters for both capture rates performed (Table 2 and Table 4), and one table showing the equipment sizing calculated by the tool (Table 3 and Table 5) for the individual stacks, also for both capture rates. In the discussion section, Table 6 presents the CAPEX calculated for all the cases, and Table 7 shows the specific reboiler duty (SRD), the ratio between the amount of reboiler duty required and the amount of CO₂ captured, also for all studied cases.

4.1. Optimization Target: Energy

The first optimization target selected was Energy, and the OCTOPUS's engine tried to find the best configurations with the lowest energy demand. As mentioned before, the tool was set for two different capture rates: 90% and 95%. For the present work, it is considered that each stack has it owns CO₂ capture plant. Figure 4 shows the values obtained

for the total cost of CO₂ captured versus the CO₂ capture rate in a year for the selected cases. The first graph (a) is the result obtained for 90% capture rate, while the second (b) is related to 95% capture rate.

The case with 95% CO₂ capture rate has required more energy than the case with 90% capture rate, once it was needed more solvent to achieve reach a greater amount of CO₂. It also was needed a higher packing height for the 95% case. The need of a higher packing height and the increase on the energy demand results in a greater CAPEX, which is shown in Table 6. Although the 95% CO₂ capture rate case required more energy, the SRD for each stack between both cases, Table 7, did not change much. These results agree with the studied presented by Du, Gao, Rochelle and Bhowan [7].

Table 2 – Energy Parameters from OCTOPUS tool for the study case with optimization target: Energy

Stack ID	CO ₂ capture rate (kton/yr)		Reboiler duty (MW _{th})		Electricity	Demand
	90%	95%	90%	95%	(MW _e)	95%
1	771.55	814.44	87.84	94.01	0.67	0.73
2	120.58	127.28	14.02	14.77	0.18	0.23
3	85.77	90.54	9.9	10.37	0.09	0.1
4	152.9	161.42	17.69	18.84	0.11	0.12
5	61.73	65.16	7.12	7.47	0.06	0.07

Table 3 – Equipment Geometry from OCTOPUS tool for the study case with optimization target: Energy

Stack ID	Absorber diameter (m)	Absorber packing height (m)		Desorber diameter (m)	Desorber packing height (m)
		90%	95%		
1	10.04	17	18	5.97	12
2	6.27	18	26	3.73	12
3	4	17	20	2.38	12
4	3.24	16	18	1.93	12
5	3.17	17	19	1.89	12

a

b

Figure 4 – Total Cost of CO₂ captured vs yearly CO₂ capture rate for the study case with optimization target: Energy (a) for 90 % capture rate; (b) for 95 % capture rate;

4.2. Optimization Target: CAPEX

The second optimization target selected was CAPEX. The selection of this feature command the OCTOPUS's engine to find the best configurations with the lowest expenditure cost obtained. It was also performed for two different capture rates: 90% and 95%. Figure 5 shows the values obtained of the total cost of CO₂ captured versus the CO₂ captured rate in a year for the cases. For the present work, it is considered that each stack has it owns CO₂ capture

plant. The first graph (a) is the result obtained for 90% capture rate, while the second (b) is related to 95% capture rate.

In this scenario, the results aiming the CAPEX have shown that a minor packing height was necessary to reach the desired capture rate, Table 5, but, on the other hand, it was required a greater energy as shown on Table 4. The case with 95% CO₂ capture rate has demonstrated, in general, a slight greater energy demand than the 90% CO₂ capture rate and a bigger absorber packing height increasing the CAPEX and the SRD as shown on Table 6 and Table 7, respectively. The results obtained on this optimization for the SRD, only a small change, are also in agreement with the literature [7].

Table 4 - Energy Parameters from OCTOPUS tool for the study case with optimization target: CAPEX

Stack ID	CO ₂ capture rate (kton/yr)		Reboiler duty (MW _{th})		Electricity Demand (MW _e)	
	90%	95%	90%	95%	90%	95%
1	771.55	814.44	120.86	120.16	0.57	0.74
2	120.6	127.28	17.04	18.68	0.22	0.19
3	85.77	90.53	12.6	13.58	0.08	0.10
4	152.9	161.39	20.83	23.99	0.12	0.12
5	61.72	65.16	8.27	9.27	0.06	0.07

Table 5 - Equipment Geometry from OCTOPUS tool for the study case with optimization target: CAPEX

Stack ID	Absorber diameter (m)	Absorber packing height (m)		Desorber diameter (m)	Desorber packing height (m)
		90%	95%		
1	10.04	8	10	5.97	12
2	6.27	11	14	3.73	12
3	4	9	11	2.38	12
4	3.24	7	9	1.93	12
5	3.17	9	11	1.89	12

a

b

Figure 5 - Total Cost of CO₂ captured vs yearly CO₂ capture rate for the study case with optimization target: CAPEX (a) for 90 % capture rate; (b) for 95% captured rate

Table 6 –CAPEX estimated for the study case in all scenarios simulated

Stack ID	CAPEX (M€)			
	90%		95%	
	Energy	CAPEX	Energy	CAPEX
1	107.90	67.66	112.41	77.02
2	50.12	36.92	65.82	43.41
3	24.15	17.26	27.00	19.15
4	17.88	12.65	19.06	14.3
5	17.38	12.69	18.82	13.95

Table 7- Specific Reboiler Duty estimated for the study case in all scenarios simulated

Stack ID	SRD (MJ/kg)			
	90%		95%	
	Energy	CAPEX	Energy	CAPEX
1	3.59	4,94	3.64	4,65
2	3.67	4,53	3.66	4.63
3	3.64	4,63	3.61	4,73
4	3.65	4,30	3.68	4.69
5	3.64	4,23	3.62	4,48

4.3. Discussion

In an absorption CO₂ capture plant, there are two paths most used to achieve a fixed captured rate: (i) increase the absorber packing height, or (ii) increase the lean solvent flow, which can result in a higher energy demand on the stripper process.

In the preliminary analysis provided by OCTOPUS, these two paths can be observed on the results obtained. The cases where the energy demand was the optimization target has presented higher absorber packing height, which was necessary to achieve the desired separation once the energy demand should be the lowest one. Consequently, the equipment purchase cost was higher. When the CAPEX was the optimization target, the results has shown a smaller absorber and it was required more solvent to assure the CO₂ capture, which demanded more energy. In a real case, the decision for which path should be followed depends on other factors like the available utilities and area

The absorber sizing for each individual stack (Table 3 and Table 5) is in accord with the assumption implemented for the scale-up step, once the superficial gas velocity was maintained constant, stack 1 has the highest flue gas flow rate and it has the greater absorber diameter while stack 5 has the lowest flow rate, it has the smaller absorber diameter.

Taking a better look on Table 4 and Table 7, it can be highlighted that the energy requirement for 95% CO₂ capture rate case was smaller than the energy requirement for 90% CO₂ capture rate case. As it was mentioned before, OCTOPUS has a large databank and an engine with a search tool implemented, it does not do simulations for each case evaluated. When the optimization target is the CAPEX, the search for the minimum SRD is not on the beginning of the evaluation process. The SRD search it is after the packing height selection. For small packing height, the range of the minimum SRD can be narrow, as shown in Figure 6, which can lead the program to select a close value, not necessary the one which was the initial desired SRD. Consequently, the use of CAPEX as optimization target can provide a smaller SRD for a higher CO₂ capture rate, but the CAPEX value itself will be lower for the smallest CO₂ capture rate case as it is expected.

Figure 6 – Specific Reboiler Duty versus ratio L/G for 11%CO₂ content for a packing height of 10 meters

5. Conclusions

This paper presents the OCTOPUS tool, an online calculator that provides refineries with multiple stacks to evaluate the potential of integrated a CO₂ capture plant on their site. It was created a study case to evaluate the tool's performance and efficiency. The tool has presented a friendly user interface resulting in a good performance in a short response time to formulate the best scenarios for the proposed study case. Based on the results, OCTOPUS has shown potential to be used as helpful tool to overcome the obstacles of dealing with multiple CO₂ emissions sources showing the initial path for the CO₂ capture plant integration.

6. Future Work

There is still more work needed to be done on OCTOPUS, so it can provide a better assessment and understanding of the multiple stack problem. Some of these improvements are already being undertaken for the next version, among them it can be mentioned:

- An expansion of the database including the REALISE solvent;
- the inclusion of the whole set of equipment of the CO₂ capture plant model presented on the sizing and cost estimation step; and
- the possibilities of integration between stacks on the tool.

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